

Supporting information

On the successful pelletization of a fragile mesoporous material and its mechanical stability mechanism

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Table 1. Elemental composition of the MSU material determined by ICP-OES.

Material	Na (wt.%)	Si (wt.%)	Al (wt.%)	Si/Al (at.)
MSU	0.05	40.75	0.84	46.61